

MENTAL HEALTH OF COMMUNITY COLLEGE TRANSFER STUDENTS

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Abstract

Many university students today struggle with anxiety. Community college transfer students are not exempt from this trend. They are more frequently unprepared than traditional students for the struggle of assimilating into a new setting, which is not any more manageable when combined with their intense and demanding curriculum. Specific resources at the CSUF campus, such as Project RAISE, cater to STEM transfer students' needs by helping them familiarize themselves with the resources CSUF offers and get the most out of their educational experience. Many campus resources are dedicated to protecting the mental health of their students. Good mental health is often linked with academic success. One-on-one casual interviews with the workers of Project RAISE confirmed that the common goal amongst these students is to do well in their courses. However, many students express that their academics are not the source of their mental health issues. Numerous have expressed that campus services are in such high demand that simply getting an appointment can be troublesome, adding to their initial anxiety. With this in mind, this project aims to address students' mental health issues by improving the existing services that CSUF already has to offer.

Introduction

“Opportunity is missed by most people because it is dressed in overalls and looks like work.”

- ***Thomas Edison***

To thrive in one's academic career, at the bare minimum, students should be in a healthy mindset. Self-motivation can be credited to a student's success when transferring to a four-year institution from a community college. Taking advantage of a university's resources requires that a

student is driven to excel, but can only be achieved when doing well mentally. College organizations offer more than just assistance in the classroom, so when a student is diligent enough to take the initiative to better themselves, they will get more out of their college experience.

Anxiety is a prevalent concern among college students that can serve as an obstacle to reaching their achievements and is not any easier for students from a community college. Dr. Tara Yosso, professor of the Graduate School of Education at the University of California Riverside, highlights the prevalent inequities among students of different backgrounds. One key idea she emphasized was how "cultural capital is not just inherited or possessed by the middle class, but rather it refers to an accumulation of specific forms of knowledge, skills, and abilities that are valued by privileged groups in society." (Yosso, 2005). The idea of "cultural capital" is highly relevant in respect to community college transfer students, when recalling that the demographic of students that come from a community college is typically marginalized groups. A community college transfer student that fulfills this underrepresented description in a situation where the standard and expectation from the university may be demanding too much right away upon their transfer can be very overwhelming and increase their stress compared to a non-transfer. With this challenge in mind, "navigational capital" is the concept Dr. Yosso brings up that counters cultural capital "despite the presence of stressful events and conditions that place them at risk of doing poorly at school and, ultimately, dropping out of school" (Yosso, 2005).

Community colleges' role in a student's academic career enhances educational opportunities for many marginalized communities. It can serve as a "stepping stone" and a "source of aspiration and experiential capital for several students" to get organized and become

an ideal student before getting to a higher level (Mobley & Brawner, 2018). However, sometimes the sudden transition to a four year can put a lot of pressure on a person, and the new environment can put a lot of unfamiliar demands on a student that hinder them from success immediately. “Transfer shock was first coined in 1965 to describe the initial maladjustment that students experience upon enrolling in a 4-year institution; typically, this maladjustment (or shock) is illustrated through a lower GPA,” as described by Lukszo in her exploration to help the community college students assimilate to four-year colleges. (Lukszo and Hayes 2019). Even for the most self-motivated and diligent community college transfer student who may not even have to worry about transfer shock, reaching all the goals they set without assistance can be challenging. It must be taken into consideration that many students of community colleges are more diverse than typical students at four-year universities in that they have “multiple responsibilities in addition to school, such as raising a family or working a full-time job” (Downing *et al.*, 2020). In addition to the demands from the college classes, these outside responsibilities should not make a student ashamed to ask for assistance when the university provides resources for this very purpose.

As stated by a first-generation community college transfer student who has well accomplished transitioning to a four-year institution, “If you go and you decide that you want to take everything you can from something, then you will be prepared for anything...As long as you went there with the right attitude and you wanted to learn” (Mobley & Brawner, 2018). This statement can apply to any student trying to excel academically. Taking this mantra into the context of a college student, taking advantage of every resource a university offers, whether it is as simple as asking for help or enrolling in programs, plays a significant role in their success. Dr. Tara Yosso uses the term “navigational capital” to describe “students’ skills and abilities to

navigate social institutions, including educational spaces” (Yosso, 2015). Recognizing the challenges students face with navigating navigational capital can be a crucial first step in opening the door to becoming a more successful academic student than if they did not know how to take advantage of what their institution offers. It is imperative to look into transition-easing measures for community college transfer students at four-year institutions, like California State University Fullerton, to increase their chances of graduating and make their experience at the university level as uncomplicated as possible.

Objectives

One publication that heavily influenced this study are the concepts of navigational capital and aspirational capital, highlighting how the university is flawed when it comes to accommodating to every demographic, from Tara Yosso’s article titled *Whose culture has capital? A critical race theory discussion of community cultural wealth* (2005). Dr. Tara Yosso is a professor at the College of Graduate School of Education, where her publication draws attention to the persistent discrepancies among students from various socioeconomic backgrounds. Though this project assesses the mental health aspects of community college students, Dr. Yosso’s expression of navigational capital helped generate ideas in establishing where the systems may have fallen short in providing easily accessible resources, making the students more stressed.

Dr. Anthony Bryk's *Learning to Improve: How America's Schools Can Get Better at Getting Better* highlights six core principles that are taken into consideration when it comes to improving educational organizations. For this study, the focus is on stem students' mental health based on how well the resources within an institution serve them during their time of need. If

these campus resources worked sufficiently as they were promoted, students who feel obligated to take advantage of them would not feel unnecessarily overwhelmed. As stress seems especially prevalent among the community college transfer students demographic, the Carnegie Foundation's Six Core Principles of Improvement inspired this project by inspiring the steps to take to address transfer students' mental health issues at a four-year university (Bryk et al., 2015). The six principles that served as a rough guideline when doing research through previous publications and my findings consisted of focusing on one specific group by being "user-centered" and then expanding those revelations by seeing what within that system around that specific group works effectively (Bryk et al., 2015). With these first three principles serving as the foundation for background research, the final three principles serve as steps forward to take when it comes to improving aspects where the system appears to fall short. Numerous external factors can play a role to the detriment of a student's mindset. However, this study aims to ensure that the university can do what it can to maintain aspirational capital for its community college transfer students through a healthy mental state.

Literature Review

Anxiety Amongst STEM Community College Transfer Students

Though community college transfer students make up a large demographic in universities, it is a prevalent issue that the obstacles that transfer students face as they move toward higher education will get neglected because they are still largely invisible (Tugend, 2018). In the first year of getting adjusted to a foreign, more prominent university, transfer students have been noted to exhibit a steep decline in their grades within the first year, which is commonly known as "transfer shock" (Tobolowsky, 2012). With the STEM, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics student demographic, these students are already taking tremendously challenging coursework regarding the material. With the demanding expectations from the classes in conjunction with a new environment, STEM transfer students often need to prepare for the challenge of assimilating into a new environment so suddenly. This literature review will evaluate some of the typical problems that STEM transfer students have that often get overlooked and how the consequential anxiety can be detrimental to their educational careers.

The Neglect of Transfer Students by the University

Transfer students have historically been treated differently than students in the four-year institution since their freshman years. They are left out of the federal graduation rates for colleges and universities because they usually take longer than four years to graduate (Tugend, 2018). This is because it hurts the institutions' graduation numbers; since they want to show the public that their students graduate on time. Transfer students that take longer to graduate than traditional students feel invisible and invalid, as if they are not on the right track when everyone goes at a different pace. Because of this, they are entirely excluded from the average graduation statistics.

Not all classes that transfer students try to transfer to their new school count for credit. The new school neglects these classes, and they would have to take those classes over again. Because of this, transfer students earned about 17 more units than those who have been there since the first year for the same degree (Xu, 2018). Xu and Tugend provide excellent insight into why transfer students would be neglected by the institution and strengthen the idea from a standpoint that hurts the university's public image. This puts transfer students at an even more significant disadvantage than their peers because they have to take more classes and all the other challenges they face.

Community colleges offer affordable educational opportunities for students from low socioeconomic backgrounds and give access to historically underrepresented communities, acting as a platform for social mobility for Hispanic students (Liu, 2011). The issue is not necessarily getting into the university; approximately 65% of transfer students take up to 6 years to graduate, depicting how the complications occur post-transfer (California Community College Chancellor's Office, 2012). This excessive time it takes for a transfer student to complete a degree, even when coming in with units that should set them ahead, displays some discrepancy on the university's end that could be addressed for the betterment of their transfer student demographic. Though many factors can differ for each individual that would extend their time within an institution, a number as high as 65% of students taking six years to graduate reflects that there are potentially some issues at the university level that can be improved upon. With such a high number of transfer students taking longer than anticipated to graduate, it can add to the anxiety of an unfamiliar environment.

Anxiety and Academic Challenges Among STEM Students

Being thrown into a new college with little time to acclimate to the new environment is rough enough. In two large institutions in the United States, one of the few studies that tackle stress in STEM students revealed elevated rates of anxiety within the first year of school (Voltmer, 2019). Voltmer also emphasizes that STEM students have a burnout-related risk pattern of 27% in their third year of school. The third year of college is typically when students transfer from community colleges to four-year institutions, making it harder for STEM transfer students. Math anxiety is a significant problem for many students in STEM (Daker, 2021). A weak foundation in mathematics is a recipe for disaster as STEM students go deeper into their studies. Whether or not it may be true, society assumes that community colleges will generally have lower standards for students compared to traditional four-year schools to be successful. Many will be immediately left behind when they transfer to a four-year college because of the lack of prior knowledge that should have been taught in the first two years. Voltmer supports the notion that STEM courses are overwhelming by providing examples of burnout solely from how difficult the courses are. Daker also backs up this notion by emphasizing how community college expectations may not prepare students for the quick pace or challenges they can expect when they get to the four-year institution. However, since STEM is so broad, it would be interesting to see what STEM majors have the worst preparation that causes the most setbacks when transferring. From there, the university may take accountability and provide more resources to strengthen those weaker foundations.

Importance of being in a Well Mental State to Succeed Academically

Many published research experiments have proven the correlation between a healthy mental state and strong academic performance. Murphy from the Department of Psychiatry of Harvard Medical School emphasizes this concept by stating that students whose mental health improved due to school-based mental health programs positively impacted their academic outcomes (Murphy, 2014). The responsibilities of being a student can be enough to cause a student distress. Adding an entirely new environment requires adjusting to a large university makes the regular stress of school even more overwhelming. Another study found that students who reported severe mental distress were four times more likely to convey a decline in academic self-efficacy (Grotan, 2019). Grotan also elaborates upon this idea by explaining that some of his experimental findings were quantifiable through a Hopkins Symptom Checklist in conjunction with supportive qualitative results with a General Self-Efficacy Scale survey to see what the sources of anxiety can potentially be. Overall, experiments such as these strengthen and solidify the idea of being mentally well to do well academically. These quantitative experiments can show that even the slightest degree of being in a poor mental state can harm one's grades. However, simply recognizing that there is any anxiety is a significant first step in making any progress in improving the psychological state to allow the best academic performance.

Navigational Capital and its Influence in Navigating an Institution

The neglect of transfer students often leaves students to be self-reliant to thrive in such a setting. Professor Tara Yosso's work at the College of Graduate School of Education at UCR highlights the ongoing differences between students from different socioeconomic origins. Dr. Yosso elaborates on a student's motivation to improve oneself by defining aspirational capital as "maintaining hopes and dreams for the future, even in the face of real and perceived barriers"

(2015). Each student may succeed by maintaining the drive to ask for help. Successful academic performance can be a reflection of a student's healthy mindset. If the university offered resources that were truly as effective as they claim, perhaps more students would exhibit taking advantage of the aids to thrive in more ways beyond their mental state. Dr. Yosso supports this concept by expanding on how students can develop their aspirations, thus strengthening overall aspirational capital, by being in an environment that fosters "linguistic storytelling and advice that offer specific navigational goals to challenge (resist) oppressive conditions" (2015). Exposure to a university atmosphere provides a student with the challenges required to grow as a student. However, learning opportunities can only take this advantage to its fullest if students can effectively navigate their way to get assistance with their problems if things get too overwhelming.

Literature Review Conclusion

STEM transfer students are frequently unprepared to assimilate into a new setting, which is not made more manageable when combined with the intense demands of their demanding curriculum. Before taking any measures to provide the resources to improve the STEM transfer students' academic performance, it is vital first to understand where the anxiety is rooted and validate their emotions to understand the most effective approach. No student should be overlooked or have grades that suffer because their institution does not acknowledge them like traditional students.

Methodology

Upon doing background research from previous publications, the first three of the six core principles of improvement from Dr. Anthony Bryk's *Learning to Improve: How America's Schools Can Get Better at Getting Better* influenced the steps that were taken to gather information for this research project. The first step of investigation to attend to the first objective of Carnegie's Principle was to establish a group by being "problem-focused and user-centered" (Bryk et al., 2015). To attend to this first principle, there were conducted "empathy interviews" with the peer advisors who work at Project RAISE, a program on campus at California State University, Fullerton, that aims to help transfer students from community colleges. Project RAISE peer advisors must meet with their assigned transfer students during their first year at CSUF at least twice throughout the semester and once for transfer students returning to the program. Since the empathy interviews were done on this particular demographic of students, Carnegie's first law of being user-centered was followed as the focus started with interviewing community college transfer students who were new to a four-year institution. The purpose of the empathy interviews was to allow the peer advisors to answer the questions more casually, allowing them to be more relaxed than they would be for a traditional interview while giving the researcher an idea of what, from the campus standpoint, can be looked into. During these empathy interviews, the peer advisors revealed that many of their students had expressed a sense of being overwhelmed at least once throughout the semester, whether due to the academic demands of the university or reasons outside their academics. In these situations where the transfer student struggles, it is up to the peer advisor to properly inform them about where to go on campus to get assistance, depending on the situation.

The peer advisors confirmed that most of their meetings with the transfer students frequently refer them to what resources they should look into on campus, given the unique individual circumstances. It prompted the creation of a survey as a next step to delve further into the roots of what troubles this demographic of students the most. To gain an understanding of how well the resources were serving their students, the peer advisors of Project RAISE were asked the following questions:

1. When you speak to students, what would you say are the most frequent and/or support that students request?
2. What service on campus do you feel you have to most commonly refer your students to?
3. After you refer your students to an on campus service that they may benefit from, do they follow up with you?
4. If they do return to follow up with you, do they report that the service was fulfilling?
5. If any have reported so, what have they stated that they would like more out of the services?

By creating a survey with these types of questions, the peer reviewers' answers provide more insight into the second objective of Carnegie's Principles, "attending to variability" (Bryk et al., 2015). In the Core Principles of Improvement, the second proposition of examining variation within a system highlights what within CSUF's current system of addressing the students' needs is effectively working and where it tends to fall short the most often. By evaluating what does and does not work in the CSUF, the third core principle is also applicable as it allows us to see the system, where Dr. Bryk describes a system as an "interdependent group of items working toward a common purpose." In this case, the system consisted of the various campus resources and the common purpose to help make the campus life and transition into the

university for a student as seamless as possible. Campus resources, whether academic-based, career-targeted, or health-related, all work together to assist the student, especially during their times of struggle.

Results

When doing this initial research, one aspect that stood out was the importance of being in a good mental state to succeed academically; studies found it to work both ways, where thriving academically can take away some of the stress that comes with it.

To further look into how my coworkers go about concerns that their students bring up, I created a survey for the peer advisors at Project RAISE to gather more information about what the students typically want regarding CSUF services when allowed to reach out for help. From the people who participated, the most commonly referred to services were tutoring or helping get their foot in the door with their career through internships and resume help, followed by Counseling and Psychological Services. The question followed was whether or not students follow up with their peer advisors regarding the efficacy of the assistance provided; approximately only 42% of the students that did follow up reported that the service was fulfilling. The remainder of the students either did not follow up or thought it fell short somehow.

Rather than focusing so much on education, a more approachable first step to address the students' mental health issues is improving the existing services that CSUF offers. Moving forward, it helps understand the root of the matter regarding where CSUF is not reaching all its students aside from accessibility issues. What stood out, in particular, was that the services, CAPS, the Counseling and Psychological Services in particular, are in such high demand that simply getting an appointment can be troublesome. Regardless of why they needed to be seen by

the school therapists, students expressed that the average waiting time to meet with the CAPs staff can take up to approximately two weeks if they were lucky. By the time the students reported they could be seen, they frequently did not care about the issue that pushed them to make an appointment in the first place. Another issue that was brought to light was the matter concerning insurance. Since community college transfer students are often more marginalized and can be older, the health insurance they have, if any, is not the best. The lack of health insurance coverage is a significant matter because when it comes to the psychological service at CSUF, only the first three appointments are free before the student must pay out of pocket unless their insurance can compensate. While some students only wanted to go to CAPs for one visit, the rule of only three free visits was a substantial problem for students who had more complications that required them to be seen by a therapist regularly and only had their campus resources to rely on because of their insurance.

Reflection

The purpose of this experiment has evolved from its initial project. For my Senior Honors Project at CSUF, I wanted it centralized around the mental health surrounding the demographic of community college transfer students. Ever since I finalized the subject of mental health among students at CSUF as my final topic, I knew that the end goal should be to shed light on the subjects to open the door for ideas of what the university can do to better provide for this population of its students.

When initially investigating the anxiety and mental health issues among STEM community college transfer students, I first began to look into publications to get an idea of what I could target surrounding the case. Following the notion that doing well in academics can reduce

stress in students, I decided to take on this issue from an educational standpoint. With Dr. Maritza Lozano as my mentor, we established that improvement science would be a valuable concept to implement. The idea behind choosing improvement science was that there was potential for a new form of learning and taking in information for the incoming CSUF that could be very effective in raising their grades and easing stress around academics since the survey revealed that a significant amount of students needing help learning about the CSUF services lead to wanting to make a slight change in the course of research for this project. Upon doing the survey and uncovering that the resources have had issues attending to everyone efficiently, the improvement science method has helped navigate what to look into and see where the system could be improved upon. With matters this significant, fixing the system can benefit every student attending the institution, not just the group of community college transfer students. This study shed light on the subject, and in the event that this study is continued and elaborated upon, it would be fascinating to delve into realistic potential solutions to fix the flawed system.

Conclusion

Much of the problem navigating institutions originates within community college students being positioned as ill-prepared in an environment that was structured without them in mind, relative to traditional students. Many students needed to be made aware of the possibility of obtaining help on campus. This unawareness suggests gaps in learning about campus resources during the initial onboarding process into a four year-institution. My findings further showed that psychological services were in such high demand that there were more cases than were meant to be handled. The availability of mental health care services falling short in seeing students suggests reorganizing the existing system, perhaps adding different subcategories, as a

cost-effective first step. The driving question was originally targeting how the university can best serve community college transfer students in the most effective way possible, and further studies would help propose practical ideas to address the matter from a university standpoint.

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